

DEEP CONVOLUTIONAL OSCILLATOR: SYNTHESIZING WAVEFORMS FROM TIMBRAL DESCRIPTORS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel deep learning model for synthesizing single-cycle waveforms from timbral attributes. The motivation was to investigate a viable alternative to traditional wavetable oscillators with intuitive control. Based on a thorough literature review and practical considerations, we selected three attributes appropriate for describing timbral characteristics of steady and harmonic tones: *bright*, *warm*, and *rich*. A deep learning network was designed to map magnitudes of these attributes to single-cycle waveforms. The architecture was based on stacking of upsampling and convolutional layers to model temporal dependencies within the waveform. The network was trained on a large number of waveforms extracted from NSynth dataset. Audio features closely related to the selected attributes were used as inputs, while the custom loss function was employed to minimize the difference in normalized power spectra between outputs and training waveforms. Four models with different hyperparameters were trained and the best one was selected using the validation dataset. Further experiments with the selected model showed that synthesized waveforms generally match the input attributes well, as the mean absolute errors for normalized attributes were 0.07, 0.05, and 0.18 for *bright*, *warm*, and *rich* respectively on the testing dataset.

1. INTRODUCTION

As it has happened in many fields during the last decade, deep learning has radically influenced automated generation of sound and music. Novel models such as MidiNet [1], MuseGan [2], MusicAutobot [3], and Music Transformer [4] demonstrated an undoubted dominance of deep learning over traditional approaches in generating polyphonic music sequences, while models such as SampleRNN [5], WaveNet [6], MelNet[7] and GANSynth [8] opened an exciting world of possibilities related to autonomous synthesis of raw audio. Recent advances in the field [9] and efforts in establishing relevant datasets [10] suggest that generative deep learning might successfully

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substitute or complement traditional sound synthesis methods in the upcoming years.

These promising trends motivated the central idea of this research – to build a waveform generator with interpretable controllable parameters using deep learning. The reasons behind choosing wavetable synthesis and interpretable parameters are multiple.

1.1 Wavetable Synthesis

Although idiosyncratic to the early years of digital sound synthesis, wavetable synthesis has been recently regaining some of its past glory. This synthesis method based on the principle of periodic reproduction of single-cycle waveforms [11, 12] is an appealing addition to other types of oscillators in comprehensive architectures of modern synthesizers, due to its capability of producing a wide range of steady, harmonic tones whose timbers can change over time. The evolving timbral character can be achieved by interpolating between multiple waveforms from a wavetable and by applying different modulations to the synthesized audio signal.

Instead of reading predefined waveforms from memory, a generative oscillator based on deep learning could act as an inexhaustible, yet controllable source of waveforms which can simply substitute a traditional oscillator without affecting other components of the sound synthesizer. The synthesized waveforms can still pass through the same amplifiers and filters controlled by the same low-frequency oscillators and envelope generators. A recent study [13] introduced the concept of differentiable wavetable synthesis in which the entire synthesis process has been turned to a differentiable digital signal processing pipeline.

The notion of substituting a standard wavetable oscillator with a generative model also motivated our previous research focused on building an autoencoder for waveform generation [14]. The autoencoder was trained to reconstruct single-cycle waveforms, while its latent variables served for traversing through the waveform space, enabling interesting transitions within the synthesized sound. The downside of that approach is that latent variables lack interpretability and intuitiveness, as they do not have an easily understandable relationship with the acoustical consequence they produce. For that reason, this research takes a different direction and examines an alternative deep learning architecture, together with different training and evaluation processes aimed at achieving a generative oscillator with more intuitive parameters.

1.2 Interpretability and Intuitiveness

Even though the lack of intuitiveness especially concerns autoencoder’s latent variables, parameters of traditional synthesis methods may also pose a challenge to efficient and inspired sound design. Synthesis parameters do not necessarily bear acoustical meaning and sometimes depend on each other, so they require technical knowledge and a certain amount of effort from users. Therefore, managing numerical parameters can be a mundane and time-consuming activity [15, 16].

To mitigate this problem, a considerable number of studies have proposed various approaches to automatic selection of synthesis parameters [16-28]. Such solutions allow musicians to define desired sounds in a more intuitive way (e.g., using timbral attributes [23-28] like *bright* and *hollow*) and automatically select parameters as inputs to sound synthesizers so that the synthesized sound satisfies the given description.

Besides parameter selection, there is also a concept of so-called feature synthesizers which are capable of producing sounds directly from a given set of audio features that are either provided by the user or extracted from a target sound [29-33].

1.3 Deep Convolutional Oscillator

As a solution to innovative and flexible waveform synthesis with intuitive parameters that can easily replace or augment wavetable oscillators, this research proposes a generative deep learning network with a decoder architecture. It has been designed to map low-dimensional vectors of descriptors given as inputs to the network to single-cycle waveforms in its output layer. These descriptors serve as controllable parameters, so they have been intentionally selected to have an intuitive relationship with the desired timbre of the synthesized sound. Outputs of the network are waveforms of a fixed duration which can be upsampled or downsampled for achieving desired pitch, as it is the case with a traditional wavetable oscillator. Such raw synthesized signal is intended to pass through further modifiers like wave shapers, amplifiers, filters, and audio effects.

The expected advantages of the taken approach in comparison to traditional wavetable oscillators are 1) the ability of producing a wide variety of waveforms instead of just reproducing and combining pre-existing ones, and 2) the use of more intuitive synthesis parameters. To achieve these benefits, we propose a deep learning architecture based on convolutions and an appropriate loss function.

2. METHODOLOGY

A prerequisite for building a convolutional oscillator with intuitive parameters was to choose an appropriate set of those input parameters. Each parameter is an attribute with a belonging numerical value from 0 to 1. They are intended to allow musicians to specify the desired timbre by setting numerical values (e.g., *bright* to 0.4, *nasal* to 0.1, and *harsh* to 0.3) when using the oscillator.

When choosing appropriate attributes, it was important to consider two requirements. The first requirement is that attribute should bear acoustical meaning and thereby allow intuitive, yet expressive control over the resulting timbre.

The second requirement was that parameters can be calculated from the audio signal they define. In other words, parameters should be related to numerical audio features. This is an opposite direction to the intended use of the parameters, but this requirement entails an important positive consequence. This way, we can calculate ideal values of parameters for training example and thereby form the training set without manual labeling. In addition, having such objective target values, they can be used for consistent evaluation of results. To find parameters which satisfy both the aforementioned criteria, we reviewed the existing literature searching for audio features with proven relations to timbral semantic scales. For selected features developed feature extractors adjusted to the use with single-cycle waveforms.

The next step was constructing a well-distributed dataset for training and testing of the deep learning model. A set of waveforms was extracted from NSynth [10], a widely used dataset which contains a large number of annotated tones systematically recorded from commercial sample libraries. The extraction algorithm ensured that selected portions of snippets from the dataset have characteristics of single-cycle waveforms. Along with each extracted waveforms we also stored their audio features calculated using custom feature extractors.

After the dataset construction, the third step was to prepare multiple neural networks with different architectures and hyperparameters. We opted with four different versions with convolutional and upsampling layers, inspired by the architecture of a convolutional decoder. We defined and implemented a custom loss function, as well as a specific scoring measure used for validation. After training all variants with the training dataset, we used validation sets to compare the models and select the best one. Finally, we evaluated the winning model using the test data and qualitatively analyzed their generative capability.

3. INPUT PARAMETERS

Semantic scales for describing musical timbres of steady tones have been a subject of scientific research for more than a century [34, 35]. Using dimensionality reduction methods such as cluster analysis [35-37], principal component analysis [39-41], and factor analysis [42], researchers have proposed concise sets of interpretable attributes for describing musical timbres. The most common conceptual labels in the examined papers were related to luminance, texture, temperature, and width. These dimensions served as a starting point for choosing attributes for controlling the generative oscillator.

Before fixing the set of attributes, we considered audio features which related to the most common semantic scales by following the directions from the previous studies [43, 44] which also overlap with practices in more recent studies on generative synthesis [45] and oscillator theory [46]. The limitation of working with repeated single-cycle waveforms is the lack of temporal changes longer than one cycle which excluded audio features such as spectral flux and inharmonicity. Based on relevance of semantic scales and appropriateness of corresponding audio features, we finally opted for three attributes: *bright* (luminance), *warm* (temperature), and *rich* (width). These attributes are not

sufficient to describe more complex and evolving sounds, but it is not their purpose anyway. The attributes are used only as inputs to the generative oscillator and can be observed as a substitution to wavetable and waveform indices in traditional wavetable oscillators.

The audio features selected in relationship to the attributes were spectral centroid, relative energy of odd-numbered partials, and spectral spread. The spectral centroid represents the gravity center of a frequency spectrum and therefore indicates the relative balance of low- and high-frequency energy. This feature is correlated with the impression of brightness [47]. The relative strength of odd-numbered partials is calculated as a ratio between the summed magnitudes of odd-numbered partials and the sum of all partials. It correlates with the perception of fullness or warmth of the sound [48]. Finally, the spectral spread is the standard deviation of the signal spectrum which indicates pureness or richness of the sound [49].

To extract these features from single-cycles waveforms, the algorithm first concatenates six repetitions of the waveform to increase the resolution of the discrete spectrum, applies the Hanning window, calculates the Fast Fourier Transform, and extracts audio features. As audio features can have different ranges of values and some can be perceived logarithmically, we transform them to fit the range [0, 1] and to achieve a linear relation to sound perception following the same approach as in similar studies [24, 50].

4. DATASET PREPARATION

Waveforms for training, validation and testing of deep learning models were extracted from NSynth dataset [10] which contains 305979 four-second, monophonic snippets taken at the sampling frequency of 16 kHz. Each snippet encompasses a tone recorded from one of 1006 instruments with a known MIDI velocity (one of five predefined levels) and a known MIDI pitch (between 21 and 108). To achieve the same duration of waveforms in the dataset, we selected snippets with MIDI note 31 (G1) from all available instruments and velocities. We opted for such a lower note to have a longer waveform size. This helps with restraining interpolation errors that may happen when the synthesized waveform is reproduced at a frequency different than its original frequency.

To determine positions of single-cycle waveforms to be extracted from snippets, the algorithm does two steps. First, it selects five random positions between timestamps of 0.5 and 2 seconds to avoid transients at the beginning of the tone and decay phase after its release. Then it uses each of random positions as the starting point for searching for the sample with the minimal absolute amplitude within next 327 samples (to encompass one full cycle for G1 at 16 kHz). This way we ensure that each waveform starts with a sample with a value close to zero. The sample with the lowest absolute amplitude is taken as the starting sample of a waveform. The periodicity is confirmed by calculating linear correlation with the neighboring blocks of samples to ensure that each waveform was taken from the steady part of the tone. The next step was the interpolation used to raise the fundamental frequency from 49 Hz to 50 Hz so that the cycle length becomes an integer number at the given sampling frequency of 16 kHz, specifically, 320

samples pre cycle. Waveforms with all zero values were removed from the dataset.

We split the extracted waveforms from the into the training, validation, and testing sets following the categorization of the corresponding snippets in NSynth dataset. After removing empty waveforms, this process resulted with 14430, 736, and 232 waveforms in the training, validation, and testing sets, respectively. For each waveform, we calculated and stored their feature vector as described in the previous section. Figure 1 shows three randomly selected waveforms and their feature vector.

Figure 1. Three randomly selected waveforms from the training set with their attributes obtained from the extracted spectral audio features.

5. CONVOLUTIONAL DECODER

5.1 Architecture

The purpose of the deep neural network proposed within this research is to produce raw single-cycle waveforms based on given input parameters. Therefore, the network has 3 inputs and up to 318 outputs which represent individual samples of the waveform with possible values between -1 and 1. Since it maps a low-dimensional input vector to an output of a higher dimensionality, the network’s structure was inspired by decoders [51].

Figure 2. Architecture of the deep convolutional waveform generator.

The first hidden layer was fully connected with the inputs, while the rest of the network was constructed by stacking multiple pairs of upsampling and convolutional layers on top of each other. Convolutional layers turned to be very efficient in handling temporal dependencies in audio signals [6] and musical sequences [1]. Unlike their typical use in obtaining more condensed representations, here we deal with a reverse problem – mapping a low-dimensional representation to a full signal. For that reason, we

altered upsampling layers with convolutional layers (with short kernels) multiple times (Figure 2) so that the network can gradually, through multiple layers, capture dependencies on various time spans within the waveform.

The fully connected layer had 22 neurons, while each upsampling layer doubled the length in comparison to the previous layer. After the last convolutional layer from the aforementioned stack, we added an additional convolutional layer without upsampling with only one convolutional filter and with a slightly longer kernel to smooth the waveform. All the layers used the hyperbolic tangent activation.

To avoid artifacts in the output waveform that could appear as a consequence of padding in the convolutional layers, we decided to avoid any padding. A negative side effect is that sizes of convolutional kernels affect sizes of subsequent convolutional layers and eventually the size of the final output of the network. However, this problem manifests only during the exploration phase in which we validate various kernels. Once when we opt for our final model, the problem is no longer relevant.

In order to test different variations based on the described architecture, we constructed, trained, and validated four models with different numbers of filters and kernel sizes in convolutional layers as shown in Table 1.

Model	Number of filters	Kernel sizes
Model 1	2, 4, 8, 16, 16, 1	2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 4
Model 2	8, 16, 32, 64, 64, 1	2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 4
Model 3	2, 4, 8, 16, 16, 1	4, 4, 4, 4, 4, 8
Model 4	8, 16, 32, 64, 64, 1	4, 4, 4, 4, 4, 8

Table 1. For each model, the corresponding row shows the number of filters and kernel sizes per convolutional layer (starting from the one closest to the input of the network).

5.2 Loss Function

Audio features do not uniquely describe waveforms. Radically different waveforms can have similar or even same audio spectral features (e.g., waveforms with shifted phases). For that reason, input parameters of the convolutional oscillator do not uniquely define the exact waveform on the output of the network. Instead, various outputs are acceptable, as long as they satisfy the input description to some extent. For example, if the attribute *bright* is set to 0.9, the user expects any waveform that with a very high spectral centroid, and not one specific waveform. This phenomenon affected the selection of the loss function, as we could not simply use a regression loss calculated by sample-wise comparison between the training waveform and the output waveform.

Instead, we opted for the mean squared error between their normalized power spectra. Discrete Fourier Transform is differentiable which makes it appropriate for a loss function that allows training with a gradient descent. Also, by using the full spectra instead of the three selected spectral features, the network has a chance to learn how to

produce waveform with the spectral distribution similar to one from the training set.

To get the power spectrum, the algorithm concatenates six repetitions of the waveform to increase the resolution, applies the Hanning window, calculates the Fast Fourier Transform, and calculates the normalized power spectrum. The loss function returns the mean squared error between corresponding discrete frequency components of these two normalized power spectra.

5.3 Training

The training of all four models was conducted using 14430 waveforms from the training set and their audio features as inputs to the network. We employed the Adam optimizer with the learning rate of 0.001. The batch size was 64, while the number of epochs was 20 to capture the convergence of the loss during the training process. The training time on Intel® Core™ i5-8250U CPU@1.60 GHz using TensorFlow 2.7.0 took between 107 seconds per epoch on average for Model 1 and 119 seconds per epoch on average for Model 4.

5.4 Validation

For validation and testing we used a scoring metric different from the loss function. The purpose of this metric was to indicate how well waveforms produced by the neural network satisfy the input parameters. For that reason, we opted for a mean absolute error (MAE) between the input parameters and the corresponding audio features of the synthesized waveform. It is important to note that waveforms from the validation set were used only to obtain their audio features so that we can validate the models based on realistic distribution of the features.

All models performed well on the validation set with regards to the selected metric, suggesting that they did not overfit to the training data. Table 2 shows the MAE per attribute per model. Based on these results, we selected Model 1 for testing and further analysis.

Model	Bright	Warm	Rich
Model 1	0.08	0.07	0.19
Model 2	0.14	0.08	0.29
Model 3	0.14	0.07	0.3
Model 4	0.15	0.07	0.28

Table 2. Mean absolute error between the input parameters and features of the output waveforms per attribute for each trained model.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Metrics

After selecting Model 1, it was evaluated using features of 232 waveforms from the testing dataset which had not been previously used neither for training, nor for the model selection. The mean absolute errors obtained on the testing

set were 0.07, 0.05, and 0.18 for attributes *bright*, *warm*, and *rich* respectively.

While the presented MAE indicates how close the spectral characteristics of the generated waveforms are to the input requirement, we were also interested to which extent these characteristics correlate to magnitudes of input attributes, so the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated for each attribute. As expected, strong or very strong positive correlations occurred: 0.77 for *bright*, 0.97 for *warm*, and 0.43 for *rich*. Such results can be interpreted in a way that by increasing the parameters for brightness, warmth, and richness, the generated waveform becomes expectedly brighter, warmer, and richer.

The inference time was measured on Intel® Core™ i5-8250U CPU@1.60 GHz using TensorFlow 2.7.0. An inference step took on average 86 μ s, which is an order of magnitude faster than what it takes to reproduce a waveform of 320 samples at the sampling frequency of 16 kHz. This finding confirms that the generative convolutional oscillator works sufficiently fast to replace a traditional wavetable oscillator in synthesizers running on PC platforms.

6.2 Generative Capabilities

To analyze the generative capabilities of the convolutional oscillator, we uniformly sampled the whole space of input parameters by iterating through 20 equidistant points for each parameter. This process resulted with the total of 8000 triples of parameters which we used as inputs to the generative model in order to analyze the distribution of its outputs.

Figure 3. Columns from left to right: 1) values of input parameters, 2) generated waveforms, and 3) first 500 Hz of their normalized power spectra (obtained from the waveforms repeated for multiple times at the constant, original frequency).

By observing generated waveforms, we found an interesting pattern. Larger sudden changes in neighboring samples most often happen in several specific positions within the waveform. This is most likely the consequence of the network architecture with upsampling layers and convolutions with short kernels. Besides these patterns, the diversity of the generated waveform shapes was significant. Figure 3 shows four selected waveforms generated from the given inputs along with relevant parts of their power spectra. The spectra were obtained by repeating the waveforms at the constant, original frequency, so its harmonics expectedly lie on the same positions, but have different magnitudes. The sound examples available online (<https://tinyurl.com/DeepConvOsc>) demonstrate multiple steady tones (including those from Figure 3) and several swipes through various input parameters.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

As a solution to generating a wide range of waveforms based on an intuitive input description, this paper proposes a novel architecture for a deep learning network. Even though the network has never received real-world waveforms as inputs or outputs during the learning process, it managed to learn how to produce viable waveforms. The generated waveforms generally match the input parameters well when the parameters are drawn from a realistic distribution, as it was the case with our training, validation, and testing data sets. While the results on the validation and test sets are very promising, the future work should investigate how the network will perform on inputs that are not drawn from a real-world distribution. The performance on arbitrary input parameters is expected to drop, since the network has been trained on audio features extracted from real signals in which some interdependencies inherently occurred.

The fact that the network managed to learn a complex mapping from a very low-dimensional space to the space of full single-cycle waveforms is due to its architecture. Alternations between upsampling and convolutional layers allow the network to construct waveforms taking into account their global and local structure. An idea for the future work is to consider further improvements of the architecture so that the network can directly benefit from thousands of real waveforms available in the training set. For example, such an architecture could be based on a convolutional variational autoencoder with additional modifications for connecting the input parameters with the latent space.

In conclusion, the convolutional generative network presented in this paper seems to have satisfactory generative capability. Due to its small size and computational efficiency, such a network can easily replace a traditional wavetable oscillator. While the notion of a convolutional generative network for waveform synthesis seems promising, further research is needed to investigate and possibly improve its performance on arbitrary inputs.

8. REFERENCES

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